

(Guiding the traveler to the most honorable path in the jurisprudence of Imam Malik.) إرشاد السالك إلى أشرف المسالك في فقه الإمام مالك

also known as "Irshad al-Salik ila Ashraf al-Masalik"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Arabic, Text, Language, Islamic Traditions, Fiqh

The book was written in the Maliki School of Law to discuss several themes of Islamic jurisprudence that concentrated on the Islamic method of worship (Ibadat) that analyzed manners of purification, principles of Islamic prayers, Obligatory and voluntary charity, fasting and Hajj and Umrah performance at the sacred place of Mecca and the rest of their likes. The other section of the text discussed the principles of social interaction (Mu'amalat), which concentrated on the system of Islamic inheritance, economic system, marital relation Judgment, and other vividly explained principles of mutual interaction with fellow humans.

Date Range: 1246 CE - 1332 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: يهوزا بن سعيد (2005) فتح الجواد في شرح الإرشاد. كانوا نيجريا

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ebook.univeyes.com/121261#>

– Source 1 Description: عبد الرحمان بن عسكري (1332). إرشاد السالك إلى أشرف المسالك في فقه الإمام مالك. دار الفضيحة القاهرة مصر

– Source 2 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/3925bd6b43fa38753f574e304ecc39671019c182/1/afd640e0d5c01d52a4240324eca

– Source 2 Description: ابن الحجر الحيثمي. (2005). فتح الجواد بشرح الإرشاد. دار الكتب العلمية. بيروت لبنان

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/9bc2c0e259ddf935950ec59ec83ab6c32c1f73a8/3/ca804128bdd24234f223606fcfl

– Source 1 Description: عبد الرحمان بن عسكري (2017). إرشاد السالك إلى أشرف المسالك في فقه الإمام مالك للبيغدادي. الملكية الفكرية محفوظة لمؤلف الكتاب

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: White.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

- No
- ↳ Shrine
 - No
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - Yes
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– Yes

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: Bookshops

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?
– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?
– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?
– Yes

Notes: Islamic state of Baghdad had supported the production of the text for the spreading of the Islamic knowledge.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?
– Yes

Notes: A token sum was paid to the copyist to help them carry out their efforts of replicating the text of Islamic Jurisprudence.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
– Yes

Notes: Several centers were formed to assist in the replication of the book.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?
– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?
– Yes

- ↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?
 - No

- ↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The document served as the basis for the state's statutes and regulations.

- ↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...
 - No

- ↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present full-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - No
 - ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - No
 - ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

–Total audience: 20000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

–Number: 20000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 20000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

–Number: 90

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 10

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 18000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Birthrate and Deathrate.

↳ Nature of audience
[select all that apply]
– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?
– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The reward of proselytization is only awarded in the hereafter.
- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
 - No
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
 - No
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
 - Yes

Notes: Proselytization is aimed at the entire non-Muslims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The text encouraged adherents towards proselytization to increase the population of Muslims.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: Designation was made on the cover page of the text.

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: A calligraphical style was applied to design the name of the text on the front page.

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions of the text accompanied commentaries, while some contained the actual text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions accompanied commentaries, while others remained plain text.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions are older than others, especially those manually written.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The content remained the same except for the accompanying commentaries.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: All the versions of the text are considered proper.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The book was a single copy written in the aspect of Islamic Jurisprudence.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the text written on Islamic Jurisprudence.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Islamic Jurisprudence.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text presented guiding principles for performing ritual prayers, fasting, and Hajj.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text is meant to guide the entire Muslims on Islamic Jurisprudence.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text express legal codes that are applicable in the Islamic State.

Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Yes

Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictate by the legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text separated a chapter on Islamic adjudication.

Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– Yes

Notes: The text express punishment of adultery, fornication, apostacy etc.

Execution?

– Yes

Notes: Execution is done on those that killed other persons illegally.

Exile?

– Yes

Notes: Exile is applied to those who commit adultery.

Corporal punishments?

– Yes

Notes: One hundred lashes are applied on those committed fornication.

↳ Ostracism?

– No

↳ Seizure of property?

– Yes

Notes: The due amount of Zakat is being collected by force from the defaulters of the obligatory charity.

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The mentioned rewards are determined in heaven.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar determined the approved date of the naming ceremony for the newborn babies on the seventh day of the birth.

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Notes: The calendar identified the seventh day of his birth as the appropriate data for the first haircuts.

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

Notes: Funerary service is done immediately after the confirmation of death.

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar determines the event of the annual Eid festivals.

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: 2

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Notes: The festivals are held at the Eid al-Kabir and Eid al-fitr occasions.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 20000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– No

Notes: Feasting is not necessary but recommendable to the people.

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

Notes: The determined calendar stipulates the period of the obligatory pilgrimage (Hajj) and leader pilgrimage (Umrah).

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: The pilgrimage is obligatory for those having the means of attendance.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: Many jurisprudential reasons are behind the existence of the text.

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done at the sacred place of Mecca.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done by walking and other means, depending on the person's fitness.

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit mind is not perishable after death.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit body is not visible.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit coexists with the material body to establish the sustainable life of the human personality.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned divine judgment, Hellfire, and Paradise.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The space is not known.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: Afterlife is ascertained by the religious group.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The language is unanimously agreed as Arabic.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The treatment is not beyond the washing, shrouding, prayer, and final burial of the dead body.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Washing of the body, shrouding, funeral prayer, and burial.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: Burial is done at the graveyard.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Notes: The practice is done to rest the body in the grave, not for worship or other motives.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned Angels and jinns as part of the supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The text identified Allah as the High God worthy to worship alone.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic

terms

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the nature of the High God.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: Monarchs are part of His servants who are mandated to worship in the same manner prescribed in the religion.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Notes: Elites are part of the servants of the Supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Power of creation

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Nothing escapes the knowledge of the High God.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: The knowledge extends to the entire activities of humans.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

Notes: The power of the High God designs the destiny of the entire creatures.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
 - Notes: Negative feelings were not appropriate for the Highest God.
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: He provides means of living to the creations.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Supreme High God communicates to humans through the prophets

and messengers.

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
 - No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Jinns.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - No
 - Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are invisible to humans except when they change to another nature.
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: .dyanybo any ot communicate may They

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: .tanceAssis

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Animals and Trees.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
Notes: Angels have no desire, but jinns reproduce through sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural beings record sin against the act of lying.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings hate laziness.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sin is recorded against the practice.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sin is recorded against the practice.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: .Humans

– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings mete out punishment on the directives of the supreme High God.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes

Notes: The actual reward of the good deeds is awarded at the hereafter, but some parts of the dividends might be enjoyed in the lifetime.

- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Better life.

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - Notes: They only record good deeds for the God to award reward.
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

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↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: .nesshappi Eternal

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - No
 - ↳ Other?
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Imam Mahadi is believed to be the Messiah in the religion.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The actual time and whereabouts are not known.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: The messiah saves humans from the evil effects of the devil.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The text did not identify a specific time of the eschaton.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world
– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– No

↳ Establishment of new political system
– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?
– Specify: Hellfire and Paradise.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– Yes

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed celibacy on unmarried people.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text did not restrict sexual activity to the married except during the menstrual or period of childbirth bleeding.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires fasting in the month of Ramadan.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires the sacrifice of property in obligatory charity (Zakat).

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires attendance of regular obligatory prayers.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires risk-taking in the stance of Jihad.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires regular attendance of regular daily prayers.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Notes: The intervals depend on the prayers: Morning prayer to Noon Prayer is 7 hours, Noon to evening is 2 hours, Evening to Sunset prayer is 3 hours, and Sunset to night prayer is 1 hour.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Only non-Muslims attempt to destroy the text.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized obligatory and non-obligatory charity to relieve the needy from life's hardship.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: The text institutionalized obligatory and voluntary charity to relieve people from poverty.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The text recommended care for the elderly and infirm people.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Charity.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Formal Islamic Schools of the caliphate set the text among the curriculum of the study to the students.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text identified some aspects of the syllabus of the Islamic jurisprudential course which formal educational Institutions impart to the people.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: Education is meant for both Male and Female gender.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The reward of teachers is in heaven.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Notes: Bureaucracy is expected to rule on the guidelines of the text.

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

Notes: The text directed mutual obedience of the adherents to the directives of the bureaucracy that did not deviate from the Shari'ah principles.

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– Yes

Notes: The text had it that all the entire incomes must comply with the principles of the

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– Yes

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: The text advocates for the judicious utilization of water resources in the cultivation of lands.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: The only restriction was made on the unauthorized movement of women in the general public.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

– Specify: Commerce and Trading.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentioned some tribute to aid in generating financial resources from the citizens.

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– No

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text separated a chapter on the principles of Jihad (holy wars).

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– Yes

↳ Power to conscript?

– No

- ↳ Maintain a full-time military corps (E.g. Swiss Guard):
 - Yes
- ↳ Maintain a standing army?
 - No
- ↳ Particular types of training/readiness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
 - Yes

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?
 - Yes
- ↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]
 - Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards
- ↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?
 - No
- ↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?
 - Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

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